

THE PEAS THAT ARE ON THE ROADS OF THE CAR AND MAKE THEM ELIMINATE

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Abstract: *This article, it is stated that the analysis of the world experience of construction and exploitation of motor roads in the Republic, deformation and violation of coatings have a serious impact on the development of these defects, non-compliance with the requirements of the period of exploitation and non-timely repair. The article points out that the analysis of the world experience of the construction and exploitation of motor roads in the Republic, the deformation and deterioration of the coatings have a serious impact on the development of these defects, non-compliance with the requirements of the exploitation period and non-timely repair.*

Keywords: *highways, deformation of pavements, pavement, automobile roads, coating deformation, mineral powder, grain composition.*

The emergence of violations in the pavement of highways worsens the fluency, decreases the speed and comfort of movement, increases the costs of using highways and carstiradi, decreases the anxiety of movementtirib, increased traffic accidentstiradi.

Road coatings are one of the causes of rapid deformation and deterioration in the following years – a change in the conditions of their operation. The traffic flow varies in quantity and quality, the speed of movement, the load on which the vehicle shoots, the speed of the account movement, the light weight and the dynamic capacity of the trucks increase. Low-load-bearing, multi-axle trucks, comfortable tourist buses increased. Foreign cars with high dynamic characteristics in the structure of the traffic flow are increasing. This is due to the fact that the axle in the cars is larger than the loading standard.

The coating is deformed when the stresses falling on the coatings from vehicles and natural-climatic factors increase from the permissible norms. As a result of changes in air temperature in different seasons of the year, freezing and melting processes occur in coatings, voltages are formed in asphalt concrete coatings and accelerate the development processes of the ingots on the surface of the screed.

1-picture. The peas on the highways.

Plastic deformation occurs due to the fact that the asphalt concrete coating is an elastic-plastic material, the properties change in the processes of overheating-cooling, the transition from a brittle state to a plastic State. The resistance of the Bunda coating to deformation will depend on the duration of exposure of various loads.

In the hot Times of the year, the coating temperature rises significantly, asphalt concrete softens and residual deformation accumulates, which continues to affect vehicles.

As is known from the experience of the use of highways, many visible violations of asphalt concrete coatings occur in the form of cracks, grooves, abrasions and traces of wheels (collea). Of state and local importance is the formation of traces of lorries on the edges of highways, along which there are many troughs. At intersections on city roads and streets, at railway crossings, in front of traffic lights, as a result of sharp braking of cars and the start of walking, the surface layers of the glued coating are pushed, waves are formed. Horizontal and vertical forces are formed from the helix of the cars. These forces will be due to the speed before the braking of cars, the intensity of braking, the longitudinal slope of the road. The deformation and distortion of urban highways contributes to the abundance of large-capacity passenger vehicles in the flow of traffic.

In the deformation and absorption of asphalt concrete coatings, the shortcomings of the norms for the design of highways can also be an important factor. One of them is the uniformity of the quantities of loads allowed by one arrow for different straps.

From the analysis of the world experience of exploitation of motor roads it is known that failure to comply with the requirements for the period of exploitation and untimely repair will seriously affect the deformation and deterioration of the pavements and the development of these defects.

In summary, the issue of finding materials that can withstand abrasion, abrasion, plastic deformation when the air temperature on the coatings is high is an important problem facing the fan.

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